

EFFORTS OF ISLAMIC RELIGIOUS EDUCATION TEACHERS IN OVERCOMING STUDENTS' DIFFICULTIES IN READING AND WRITING THE QURAN AT SD AL-ITTIHADIAH LAUT DENDANG

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Abstract

In an effort to improve the ability to read and write the Qur'an in students, it cannot be separated from the efforts of teachers. Where this is a process of maturing students through learning to optimize the potential that exists in students so that character, character and personality are formed, where this requires a holistic strategy so that the learning process can run optimally. Where the role of Islamic Religious Education teachers is very important in forming a strategy, building conducive interactions to overcoming the impact of difficulties in reading and writing the Qur'an among students. The research method used is qualitative with a descriptive approach. Data collection techniques include observation, in-depth interviews, and documentation. Research findings describe new information obtained from the research process, which is based on data collection that makes it knowledge.

Keywords: *Effort, Islamic religious education teacher, Difficulty reading and writing the Qur'an*

Introduction

Nowadays, the future generation of the nation looks very concerning, and this concern does not arise without reason. This is clearly evidenced by observing the social situation, which is increasingly far from the rules. For example, cases of highway robbery or muggings cause anxiety among drivers, and unexpectedly, the perpetrators are still underage. Another case is brawls between communities that result in casualties. If this continues to be left unchecked, Indonesia will find it difficult to create a golden generation. Besides natural disasters, social disasters that emerge in society will become a new challenge. We can avoid such situations and conditions by starting to pay attention to education, because education is the foundation for someone to think logically in taking action. Nowadays, education for every child can be obtained from family and school. However, the fact is that not all families realize the importance of educating directly. As a result, schools are expected to provide perfect education for every student. In Islam, of course, it is not burdensome for those who want to seek knowledge; in fact, Allah has arranged everything. Allah has provided a blueprint, and Allah has given us guidance through the Qur'an. With this guidance, we can follow the teachings and attain the pleasure of Allah SWT. However, in utilizing the contents of the Qur'an, a person must have the ability to read, understand, and write the Qur'an. This is because with the ability to read and understand, a person can more easily navigate life, and with the ability to write, their memory will be stronger and they can spread knowledge through writing.

This aligns with the opinion of Fauzi and Ramadhani, who stated that the ability to read and write are skills that must be learned intentionally. It is different from learning to speak; the abilities to listen and speak are skills acquired naturally. (Fauzi, A., & Ramadhani, 2021). In teaching reading and writing, teachers are the key to learning in schools. The success of an education is largely determined by the affectionate relationship between teachers and students. This relationship makes students feel secure so they are not afraid of their teachers or avoid learning. (Ainiyah, 2022). A teacher is not only an instructor, but also an educator. Therefore, in Islam, a person can become a teacher not just because they have met the academic and knowledge qualifications, but more importantly, they must have commendable character. (Firmansyah, M., & Lestari, 2022). This research aligns with the study by ricky and angngel in 2022 on the role of teachers in improving the quality of education, which states that a teacher's role can be implemented by reflecting on their own

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existence, assessing the situation to rise, and starting to think about the steps that need to be taken when facing difficulties in learning. (mallisa & rani, 2022). Then, the importance of islamic religious education is explained by Syawwaliyah Herzawati (2022), who stated that Islamic religious education is carried out so that the millennial generation does not fall into undesirable negative things and can have ethics and good characteristics in accordance with the teachings of religion and the state. (Herzawati, 2022) In efforts to improve students' ability to read and write the Qur'an, teachers also play an essential role. Effective strategies are needed to optimize the potential within students so that their character, personality, and traits as complete human beings are developed, allowing the learning process to proceed effectively. (Martapura, 2024). especially since the students in question are elementary school children, who generally still lack the skills and require extra guidance from religious teachers to improve their ability to read the Qur'an. However, in every learning process, there are certainly difficulties experienced, both in terms of the students' abilities and in the implementation of the learning process.

Based on this, the researcher is interested in conducting a study with the aim of addressing the problems that arise in learning Quranic reading and writing. Unlike previous studies, this research has a novelty, namely covering the importance of the role of teachers and Islamic religious education, as well as other factors that hinder the learning process and the efforts made as solutions to these problems. There are three issues in this study: (1) What efforts are made by Islamic Religious Education teachers in overcoming difficulties in Quranic reading and writing for students at SD Al-Ittihadiyah Laut Dendang? (2) How is the interaction between teachers and students regarding the development of Quranic reading and writing skills of students at SD Al-Ittihadiyah Laut Dendang? (3) What is the impact of difficulties in Quranic reading and writing on students' academic achievement and character development at SD Al-Ittihadiyah Laut Dendang? It is hoped that this research can address existing problems by analyzing the efforts made by Islamic education teachers in overcoming difficulties in reading and writing the Qur'an for students at SD Al-Ittihadiyah Laut Dendang, as well as identifying the patterns of teacher-student interaction in Qur'an reading and writing learning and analyzing the impact of difficulties in reading and writing the Qur'an on students' achievement and character.

Method

Qualitative research with a descriptive approach. This approach allows researchers to understand phenomena that occur in the field, namely difficulties in reading and writing the Qur'an among students. A qualitative approach is chosen because it allows researchers to explore experiences and perspectives related to the phenomenon, which cannot be fully captured through quantitative methods. The descriptive approach, in turn, provides a framework for detailing the characteristics and dynamics of the researched phenomenon, without attempting to test hypotheses or measure cause-effect relationships. This research was conducted at SD Al-Ittihadiyah Laut Dendang, which served as the main site for data collection. The subjects of the study include teachers of Islamic Religious Education (PAI) subjects who are directly involved in the use of learning media, the principal who supports the development of the media, as well as elementary school students at SD Laut Dendang. To obtain accurate and comprehensive data, several data collection techniques were used, namely observation, interviews, and documentation. Through observation, the researcher directly observed the Quran learning process in the classroom, allowing them to record the interactions between teachers and students, identify any arising obstacles, and understand the overall classroom dynamics. Observations were conducted participatively, which means that the researcher not only observed from a distance but also actively participated in learning activities, allowing the researcher to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences of students and teachers. Interviews were conducted with students and teachers, aiming to explore their experiences, feelings, and perspectives regarding reading and writing difficulties in the Qur'an. Interviews with students focused on understanding their motivation, challenges, and the support they needed to succeed in learning to read the Qur'an. The questions asked were designed to uncover the specific difficulties they faced, as well as the strategies they used to overcome those difficulties.

- 1) Student Interviews: Exploring students' experiences, feelings, and difficulties in learning to read the Qur'an. Questions focus on their motivation, challenges, and the support they need.
- 2) Teacher Interviews: Understanding the strategies, methods, and efforts teachers make to overcome students' difficulties. Questions cover main obstacles, additional programs, adjustments in teaching methods, use of media, parental involvement, communication with students, motivation, student enthusiasm, the impact of difficulties in reading the Qur'an on performance, long-term effects, and ways of teaching the Qur'an.

The researcher used documentation data collection techniques, analyzing related documents such as tajwid guidebooks, lesson notes, and school programs that support Quran learning at SD Al-Ittihadiyah Laut Dendang. The data analysis technique used included data reduction, data presentation, and data verification. This study employed data validity techniques, including prolonged and extensive observation as well as triangulation, where the researcher conducted more than three visits to the location to make observations and obtain accurate data.

Results and Discussion

This study reveals several findings related to the process of learning the Qur'an among students, particularly regarding the challenges they face and the efforts made to overcome them. One of the main obstacles identified is the lack of basic knowledge in reading the Qur'an.

1. Lack of family support

This is caused by the lack of attention and guidance that students receive at home, which is often exacerbated by factors such as coming from a broken home or living with a grandmother, who may not have the resources or sufficient knowledge to provide adequate support in learning the Qur'an. This is in line with the research by Patimah et al. (2023), which states that students from broken homes have low learning motivation and need to be given positive reinforcement. (Patimah et al., 2023)

2. Lacking consistency and motivation

Students also experience difficulties in memorization, especially due to irregular schedules and low repetition frequency. Memorization practice conducted only once a week is not enough to strengthen students' memory and understanding of the Qur'anic verses. The lack of creativity of teachers in organizing learning causes students to feel bored. This aligns with Nur Aliyah's research, which states that it is important for teachers to understand what good teaching creativity looks like so that everything the teacher does benefits the learning process, particularly in building students' learning motivation. (Nur 'aliyah et al., 2017)

3. Lack of self-confidence

Emotional factors also play a role, where feelings of embarrassment when not yet fluent in reading, especially when performing in front of the class, become a significant barrier for students to actively participate in learning. Haidar and Sholeh mention that one way to foster self-confidence is by having students practice reading regularly, as this can help build their self-confidence. (Haidar & Sholeh, 2021)

In response to this challenge, teachers have implemented various efforts and strategies to help students overcome their difficulties. One of the main initiatives is the Iqro reading program, which is held regularly once a week in each class. This program aims to provide a solid foundation in Quranic reading for students who are still struggling. In addition, teachers also periodically review the hijaiyah letters and makhraj (the points of articulation of the letters) to ensure that students have a deep understanding of Arabic phonetics. The Murojaah program, which takes place every Friday morning, provides an opportunity for students who are already proficient in reading or memorizing the 30th Juz to maintain and improve their skills. A more personalized approach is also applied, where teachers give individual attention to students who need extra help, such as prioritizing them to come forward in class and providing more intensive guidance.

The use of learning media, such as tajweed guidebooks, also becomes an integral part of the learning process, helping students understand the rules of reading the Qur'an correctly. In addition, teachers also strive to create a pleasant and interactive learning atmosphere, often using a play-and-learn approach to increase student enthusiasm. This aligns with Putti et al.'s opinion, which states that it helps enhance student engagement and assists students who have difficulty developing ideas (Larasati et al., 2024). As a form of appreciation and motivation, teachers also give praise and awards to students who show progress, and provide special rewards to sixth-grade students who successfully read certain surahs fluently. With the presence of rewards, students are motivated to achieve the expected targets. In their research, Wahyu et al. noted that students appeared enthusiastic because they admitted that the learning activities were very interesting, especially with the addition of rewards for the winners and afraid of being punished if they lose (Rofikhatul Ula et al., 2022) This study also highlights the importance of the role of parents in supporting their children's Qur'an learning. The lack of parental involvement in the learning process at home becomes a significant obstacle. Many parents do not have the time or knowledge to help their children learn to read the Qur'an, thereby limiting student progress. Furthermore, the study shows that difficulties in reading the Qur'an can

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negatively affect other aspects of a student's academic life. Students who struggle with reading the Qur'an tend to have lower self-confidence and find it difficult to follow other lessons that require good reading skills. Conversely, strong Qur'an reading skills have a positive influence on students' character and morals, helping them develop strong moral and spiritual values. Despite these challenges, the study also found that most students showed enthusiasm in learning to read the Qur'an, often asking questions about the surahs they wanted to memorize. However, there was also a group of students who were less enthusiastic because they found the basics of reading Iqro difficult. The teacher made efforts to provide additional attention and support to help them overcome their difficulties. The same goes for the results of the interview with the teacher at SD Al-Ittihadiyah Laut Dendang. She said:

“As a PAI teacher, I see that the biggest challenge is how to make students interested and motivated to learn the Qur'an. Many of them come from less supportive backgrounds, so they do not have a strong foundation in reading the Qur'an. In addition, busy schedules and a lack of support from parents also pose obstacles. However, we try our best to give the best for the students. We use various creative teaching methods and media, such as letter cards, pictures, and educational games. We also give individual attention to students who need extra help. Alhamdulillah, with these efforts, many students have shown progress”.

In addition to interviews with the Islamic Education teacher, the researcher also conducted an interview with Mr. Ali Rahman, S.Pd.I, one of the Islamic Education teachers at SD Al-Ittihadiyah Laut Dendang. He explained:

“In teaching BTAQ, I see that the students' abilities are very diverse. Some are fluent in reading, but there are still many who stammer and mistakenly pronounce hijaiyah letters. The biggest challenge is how to make them dare to read without fear. For this reason, I usually accompany students personally, provide the opportunity to take turns reading, and utilize simple media such as Iqro', mushaf, and letter cards. I also always try to give them praise so that they are more confident. In my opinion, parental support is very important because home practice is much more decisive for children's development. I hope that all students can read the Qur'an fluently before they graduate from this school.”

In addition, the researcher also interviewed several students.

Keira Alesha (6th Grade) shared her experience:

“I enjoy learning to read the Qur'an at school, even though sometimes I am still afraid of making mistakes when asked to go to the front. The hardest part for me is reading the long and short recitations; sometimes I still get them wrong. The teacher usually corrects me immediately if I make a mistake, then asks me to repeat it. I become braver because the teacher always gives encouragement and praise. When I can read correctly, I feel very proud.”

Meanwhile, Ahmad Fauzi (Grade V) also gave his response:

“I find learning to recite the Quran at school enjoyable, especially when the teacher gives small rewards or stars in the book. I often have trouble distinguishing similar Arabic letters, such as dzal and dhal. The teacher is always patient in correcting my reading and does not get angry when I make mistakes. At home, my parents sometimes help me study, but not every day. My hope is that I can soon read the Quran fluently so I can participate in the recitation competition at school.”

The role of teachers in overcoming difficulties in understanding and reading the Qur'an for students can be demonstrated through their role as facilitators, which is carried out with personal guidance. This is emphasized in Surah Al-Alaq(96:1-5):

{ اِقْرَأْ بِاسْمِ رَبِّكَ الَّذِي خَلَقَ ۙ ۱ خَلَقَ الْإِنْسَانَ مِنْ عَلَقٍ ۚ ۲ قُرْ ۖ اِقْرَأْ وَرَبُّكَ الْكَرِيمُ ۚ ۳ الَّذِي عَلَّمَ بِالْقَلَمِ ۚ ۴ عَلَّمَ الْإِنْسَانَ مَا لَمْ يَعْلَمْ ۝ ۵ }

It means: 'Read in the name of your Lord who created, He created man from a clot of blood. Read, and your Lord is the Most Noble, who taught (man) by the pen, He taught man that which he did not know.”

(Kemenag,2019).

According to Ibn Kathir's interpretation, this verse emphasizes that Allah is the Lord who created humans from a clot of blood and honored them by teaching them knowledge, especially through the "pen" (writing and reading). These verses command to read and seek knowledge while remembering Allah as the source of knowledge. Knowledge is a source of human dignity and can be conveyed through reason, speech, and writing. This is in accordance with the words of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW):

الَّذِي يَقْرَأُ الْقُرْآنَ وَيُفْرَأُ لَهُ أَجْرَانِ ۖ وَالَّذِي يَقْرَأُ الْقُرْآنَ وَيُفْرَأُ لَهُ أَجْرَانِ ۖ ع فِيهِ وَمَنْ عَلَّمَهُ شَيْءًا قِي لَهُ أَجْرَانِ

“The person who is skilled in reading the Qur'an will be with the noble and obedient angels, and the person who reads the Qur'an with difficulty and finds it hard, will receive two rewards”.(HR.Bukhari No.4937)

"The best of you are those who learn the Qur'an and teach it." (HR. Bukhari No.5027)

Recognizing these challenges, Islamic Education (PAI) teachers have made various efforts to help students overcome difficulties in reading the Qur'an. These efforts include using habituation methods by repeating Qur'anic readings, familiarizing students with Arabic vocabulary, organizing extracurricular activities, providing understanding of the importance of reading the Qur'an, conducting group recitations, giving achievement cards, and engaging with students to help them read the Qur'an. Overall, the study concludes that difficulties in reading the Qur'an are caused by a combination of internal and external factors, and PAI teachers' efforts to address these difficulties are carried out through learning approaches. Reading is important for acquiring knowledge and understanding. Moreover, the Hadith of Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) states that 'The best of you are those who learn the Qur'an and teach it,' highlighting the virtue and significance of studying and practicing the teachings of the Qur'an in daily life. Thus, this research provides valuable insights into the process of learning the Qur'an and emphasizes the importance of collaborative efforts among teachers, students, parents, and the community to create a supportive environment that encourages successful Qur'an learning for all students. Through reading activities, students can obtain various information, knowledge, and new experiences. What is read allows students to enhance their thinking abilities, sharpen their perspective, and broaden their insight; besides that (Sukma, 2021). Writing is the gateway to lifelong learning and social inclusion because it can address various problems through the orchestration of cognitive processes that take into account clear demands and goals (Wibowo et al., 2025). Truly advanced education today is education that fosters a high sense of curiosity, encourages independent learning, engages in experimentation, and above all, has a critical attitude as its characteristic (Musya'adah, 2018)

Acknowledgment

This study highlights the comprehensive efforts implemented by Islamic Religious Education (PAI) teachers at SD Al-Ittihadiyah Laut Dendang in addressing the Quranic literacy challenges faced by students. These initiatives include extensive interventions, ranging from remedial programs such as learning Iqro, aimed at building a strong foundation in basic reading skills, to continuous reinforcement through the repetition of hijaiyah letters and Murojaah programs. Beyond the classical approach, teachers also apply individualized approaches tailored to the unique needs of each student, ensuring that no student is left behind. The use of innovative learning media and the creation of an enjoyable and interactive learning environment demonstrate the teachers' commitment not only to delivering the material, but also to spark students' interest and engagement. In addition, teachers consistently provide motivation and recognition to celebrate students' progress, foster self-confidence, and encourage continued effort. Furthermore, teachers consistently provide motivation and recognition to celebrate students' progress, foster self-confidence, and encourage ongoing effort.

This study also highlights the importance of positive and supportive interactions between teachers and students as a key to unlocking optimal learning potential. An approach that integrates play elements and emotional support creates an environment where students feel safe to take risks, ask questions, and learn from mistakes. This dynamic interaction not only increases students' enthusiasm for learning the Qur'an but also fosters a relationship of mutual respect and trust between teachers and students. This study also emphasizes that the success of learning the Qur'an not only depends on the efforts of teachers at school but also on the active support of parents at home. The lack of parental involvement in guiding their children in learning the Qur'an is a significant obstacle that can hinder students' progress. Consistent parental support, which includes providing resources, assisting with assignments, and emphasizing the importance of learning the Qur'an, is crucial to reinforcing school-based learning and fostering a lifelong love for the Qur'an.

Finally, this study highlights the detrimental consequences of difficulties in reading and writing the Qur'an on overall student development. Students who struggle with the Qur'an may experience negative impacts on their academic performance, as poor reading skills can affect their ability to succeed in other subjects. Moreover, difficulties with the Qur'an can hinder the development of students' character and moral values, as they may miss opportunities to understand and internalize the teachings of the Qur'an. Therefore, this study emphasizes that efforts to address difficulties in reading and writing the Qur'an should continue to be enhanced and prioritized as an important investment in the students' future.

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